

Catalogue of Obscene and Brothel Tangos

Guardia Vieja — A Classification by Mechanism of Survival and Censorship

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Translation from the Spanish original

A Note on Lunfardo and Translation

Lunfardo is the urban slang of the River Plate region, developed in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries primarily in the conventillos (tenement houses) and brothels of Buenos Aires and Montevideo. It drew on Italian, Spanish, French, Portuguese and indigenous languages, and served as a coded register among the working class, immigrants and criminal milieu. Many of its terms have no direct English equivalent.

The titles in this catalogue present a specific translation challenge: their meaning, and therefore their historical significance, depends entirely on the double entendre operating between the original title and its sanitized version. For this reason, each entry provides both the English translation and the original Spanish title in parentheses, so that the substitution mechanism — phonetic, morphological or semantic — remains visible. Where a lunfardo term has no English equivalent, it is kept in Spanish and explained in the notes. The analysis of each case is written for a reader with no prior knowledge of the language or context.

Introduction: The Problem of the Archive

Most of the lyrics that make up this catalogue do not appear in printed scores. The League of Decency (*Liga de la Decencia*) and the municipal police banned them, and publishers who wished to operate in the legal market simply did not print them.¹ What survived was the music — formalizable, exportable, marketable — and not the word, which was oral, circumstantial, and carried the full weight of what the bourgeois order needed to expel. The

¹The League of Decency (*Liga de la Decencia*) was a Catholic-inspired moral pressure organization that operated in Buenos Aires from the late nineteenth century. It held no direct policing power, but its sustained influence over music publishers, printers and the press was decisive in driving the purification of the popular repertoire. Publishers who wished to remain viable in the legal market practiced self-censorship as a matter of routine.

result is an archive biased from the outset: what reached the collections was the sanitized version, not the original.

The corpus that follows was reconstructed from three types of evidence. First, original titles that circulated in the world of the brothel and the high-end prostitution house (*lupanar*) and that in some cases survived through carelessness or through semantic obsolescence — that is, the obscene term simply fell out of use and the title stopped being readable as offensive. Second, cases where a documented sanitized version exists, allowing the original to be inferred by comparison. Third, the oral tradition of early tango musicians — the so-called *Guardia Vieja*, or Old Guard — interviewed by researchers such as José Gobello during the 1950s and 1960s.²

The most transparent evidence for how censorship worked is the comparison between an original title and its cleaned-up version. There one can see, with almost surgical clarity, the precise mechanism: phonetic substitution of a similar-sounding word, removal of a single morpheme, change of referent, or passage to instrumental form with the lyrics suppressed entirely. What this catalogue proposes is to systematize that corpus by mechanism, and to read it not as a collection of curiosities but as a historical document that reveals how cultural control over the body and sexuality operated in turn-of-the-century Buenos Aires.³

Classification System

The catalogue organizes the corpus into four categories, each defined by the mechanism that determined how a piece did — or did not — reach the historical record:

Category A: the original title was replaced by a sanitized version. Both versions are documented, making the censorship process directly visible and traceable.

Category B: the original title survived intact, but its sexual content was veiled, displaced, or simply stopped being heard as offensive over time. The obscenity persists in the word but the bourgeois ear no longer registered it.

Category C: the piece survived as music only. The lyrics were suppressed from the official record entirely; the melody circulated as an instrumental.

²Gobello, José. *Diccionario lunfardo*. Buenos Aires: Peña Lillo, 1975. Gobello founded the Academia Porteña del Lunfardo in 1962 and conducted systematic interviews with Guardia Vieja musicians during the 1950s and 1960s, while several of them were still alive. His oral compilation work is the primary source for Category D.

³Lehmann-Nitsche, Robert. *Textos eróticos del Río de la Plata* [c. 1923]. Lehmann-Nitsche was a German folklorist based in Argentina. His compilation is one of the very few systematic records of this corpus. It circulated in restricted form and was never published during the author's lifetime.

Category D: exclusively oral survival. No score, no publisher's record. These cases reached us solely through the memory of musicians who were there.

Category A — Sanitized Title (both versions documented)

Original title (EN / ES)	Sanitized title (EN / ES)	Author	Analysis
Shake My Dick for Me (<i>Sacudime la poronga</i>)	Shake My Venetian Blind for Me (<i>Sacudime la persiana</i>)	Vicente Loduca	In Buenos Aires lunfardo, <i>poronga</i> means penis. <i>Persiana</i> means venetian blind. The substitution is purely phonetic: both words begin with 'p', have four syllables, and fit the rhythm identically. The gesture described by the verb — <i>sacudime</i> , shake it for me — remains unchanged. Only the object is swapped. This is the most mechanical substitution in the corpus: a word that sounds similar replaces a word that means something obscene, with no other change whatsoever.
Dirty Cunt (<i>Concha sucia</i>)	Dirty Face (<i>Cara sucia</i>)	Casimiro Alcorta	<i>Concha</i> in River Plate Spanish is a common vulgar term for the female genitalia (equivalent to 'cunt' in English). <i>Cara</i> means face. The substitution changes one letter of the first word and entirely transforms the meaning. Casimiro Alcorta was an Afro-Argentine musician whose work circulated in both Afro-descendant and brothel contexts. ⁴ The censored version, attributed to Francisco Canaro, replaced the original with an infantile lyric about a little girl who refused to wash her face. The whitewashing operation here is simultaneously literal and symbolic: a Black musician's obscene composition is turned into a children's song. The original meaning, the original author and the original context all disappear.
The Lora's Cunt (<i>La concha de la Lora</i>)	The Face of the Moon (<i>La cara de la luna</i>)	Manuel Campoamor	<i>Lora</i> was the lunfardo code word for the Jewish women from Eastern Europe brought to Buenos Aires by the Zwi Migdal, a criminal trafficking network that operated from approximately 1906 to

⁴On Casimiro Alcorta as an Afro-Argentine musician and his role in the early history of tango, see Andrews, George Reid. *The Afro-Argentines of Buenos Aires*. Madison: University of Wisconsin Press, 1980. Alcorta's case is one of the clearest examples of how the whitewashing of tango's origins operated on multiple registers simultaneously.

Original title (EN / ES)	Sanitized title (EN / ES)	Author	Analysis
			1930. ⁵ The original title therefore simultaneously names the female genitalia, identifies a specific ethnic group, and locates the scene in a specific type of brothel that housed trafficked women. The sanitized version — 'the face of the moon' — erases all three references in a single operation: the genital reference, the ethnic reference and the trace of trafficking. This is the densest case of simultaneous censorship in the corpus.
Fuck the Old Lady (<i>Hacéle el culo a la vieja</i>)	Give the Old Lady a Curl (<i>Hacéle el rulo a la vieja</i>)	Anonymous	<i>Culo</i> means arse/anus; in this context, the phrase describes anal intercourse. <i>Rulo</i> means curl (as in a curl of hair). The two words share the same number of syllables, the same vowel pattern and the same position in the rhythmic line. The rhyme scheme of the song is completely preserved. Only the meaning changes. This is sonic censorship at its most precise: the ear hears the same shape, but the word has been replaced.
Push, It Won't Go In (<i>Empujá que no entra</i>)	Push, It's Going In (<i>Empujá que ya entra</i>)	Anonymous	The original title describes a moment of sexual resistance or difficulty during penetration: 'push, it won't go in.' The sanitized version removes the negation ('no') and replaces it with an affirmative ('ya', already/now): 'push, it's going in.' The change consists of a single word. But that word is everything: the negation is the entire sexual content of the original, describing the act with uncomfortable precision. Its removal converts a description of resistance into a description of smooth facilitation — and eliminates the tension that made the title obscene.
Shave Your 7, the 8 Is a Holiday! (<i>¡Afeitate el 7 que el 8 es fiesta!</i>)	The 8 Is a Holiday (<i>El 8 es fiesta</i>)	Antonio Lagomarsino	In the lunfardo of the period, '7' and '8' were coded anatomical references: '7' designated the anus, and '8' (being rounder in shape) referred to its surroundings. 'Shave your 7 because the 8 is celebrating' is an invitation to anal grooming before sex. The sanitized version suppresses the first half of the title — the verb and its object — and keeps only the consequence: 'the 8 is a holiday.' Without the first

⁵The Zwi Migdal was a criminal organization that trafficked Jewish women from Eastern Europe — primarily Poland and Russia — into sexual slavery in Buenos Aires. It operated between approximately 1906 and 1930 with documented complicity from police and judicial authorities. The lunfardo term *lora* for these women is documented in Mirelman, Victor A. *Jewish Buenos Aires, 1890–1930*. Detroit: Wayne State University Press, 1990.

Original title (EN / ES)	Sanitized title (EN / ES)	Author	Analysis
			phrase, the title is completely opaque. Nobody can tell what is celebrating or why.
Twice Without Taking It Out (<i>Dos sin sacarla</i>)	Twice Without Removing (<i>Dos sin sacar</i>)	Oral tradition	The original title describes male sexual performance in the brothel context: performing the sexual act twice without withdrawing. The entire obscene meaning is carried by a single word: <i>la</i> , the feminine pronoun that refers to the penis (in Spanish, the object being kept inside). The sanitized version removes this one word. Without it, the title means nothing in particular — just 'two without removing,' which could refer to anything. Censorship operated here on a single morpheme: one word removed, all meaning lost.
Mister Commissioner (<i>Señor Comisario</i>)	Canaro/Caruso version (lyrics modified)	Oral tradition	The original lyrics included the line ' <i>no coge conmigo</i> ' — 'he won't fuck with me' — a direct complaint addressed to a police commissioner, presumably about a client or a pimp. In the Buenos Aires brothel context, the commissioner was a figure of ambiguous authority: officially responsible for regulating prostitution, in practice often complicit in it. The later version associated with Canaro and Caruso suppressed the explicit sexual references while keeping the title. The original charge against the commissioner — whatever it was — became unreadable.

Category B — Title Preserved, Content Concealed

In these cases no external intervention suppressed or modified the title. The original survived — but over time, the sexual meaning became inaudible to mainstream ears, either because the lunfardo term fell out of use or because the cultural context that made the reference legible disappeared.

Title (EN / ES)	Author / Reference	Analysis
The Corn Cob (<i>El Choclo</i>)	Ángel Villoldo	<i>Choclo</i> (corn cob) was lunfardo slang for the penis. In Buenos Aires at the turn of the twentieth century, the sexual connotation of the word was widely understood. Villoldo wrote a lyric composed entirely of rural imagery — corn fields, farm workers, peasants cooking over fires — to shield the piece from censorship while preserving the double meaning in the title. The strategy worked so completely that today <i>El Choclo</i> is danced at state ceremonies and embassy receptions without anyone

Title (EN / ES)	Author / Reference	Analysis
		recalling — or wishing to recall — what the title originally named. See the detailed case study in Section 6. ⁶
Touch It for Me, Carolina (<i>Tocámela Carolina</i>)	Bernardino Terés	The imperative <i>tocámela</i> means 'touch it for me,' with the feminine pronoun referring to the penis. In the brothel context, followed by a woman's name, the instruction is unambiguous. The title survived intact in the repertoire, apparently because over time nobody was listening to it with the ears of the brothel anymore. The obscenity did not need to be removed; it simply became inaudible.
Give Me the Token (<i>Dame la lata</i>)	Lino de los Heros	<i>La lata</i> (literally 'the tin' or 'the token') was the chip or ticket system used in Buenos Aires brothels. The client paid the establishment, received a token, and handed it to the woman — a mechanism that kept the money transaction separate from the sexual act and allowed the owner to track and control the business. This is the only title in the corpus that documents the internal economic organization of the brothel. The title survived because <i>lata</i> drifted toward other meanings in everyday Spanish (it now commonly means 'nuisance' or 'tin can') and the original reference became unrecognizable to later audiences.
The Brothel (<i>El Queco</i>)	Ángel Villoldo (c. 1874)	<i>Queco</i> was lunfardo for brothel. The title names the space directly, without any metaphor or euphemism. Its survival in the standard tango repertoire is almost certainly due to the term falling completely out of use: audiences who did not know the word simply did not know what they were dancing to.

Category C — Passed to Instrumental (lyrics suppressed)

In these cases the music survived but the lyrics were entirely suppressed from the official record. The pieces circulated as instrumentals. The titles alone — often preserved by oral tradition — are the only evidence of what the words once described.

Title (EN / ES)	Author / Reference	Analysis
Here Comes Celina at the Tip (<i>Ahí va Celina en la punta</i>)	Brothel tradition	<i>Punta</i> (tip/point) carried clear sexual connotations in the lunfardo of the brothel — in this context, the tip of the penis. Celina is a woman's name, placing the scene in the brothel. The melody survived; the lyrics did not.
Let It Die Inside (<i>Dejálo morir adentro</i>)	José Di Clemente	A description of withdrawal-free intercourse, using the metaphor of dying inside. No euphemism, no mediation. The total suppression of the lyrics was the only available response. The piece survived exclusively as an instrumental.

⁶Villoldo, Ángel (1861–1919). Composer, singer and *payador* (a tradition of improvised sung verse in dialogue form), considered the first major tango composer. On his life and work, see Sierra, Luis Adolfo. *Historia de la orquesta típica*. Buenos Aires: Corregidor, 1997.

Title (EN / ES)	Author / Reference	Analysis
Seven Inches (<i>Siete pulgadas</i>)	A. Bevilacqua	A direct reference to penis size. The title requires no decoding. Passed to instrumental without leaving any recorded lyrics.
What a Fuck with All This Wind (<i>Qué polvo con tanto viento</i>)	Brothel tradition	<i>Polvo</i> (literally 'dust') was already common slang for the sexual act in River Plate Spanish by 1890, exactly as it remains today. The title is explicit on its face. Survived as an instrumental.
The Pudding Mold (<i>La budinera</i>)	Riverside tradition	<i>Budinera</i> : a cylindrical baking mold with a hole in the center, used for making puddings and cakes. As a metaphor for the female genitalia, the shape made the reference self-explanatory. Instrumental survival only.
Push the Iron All the Way In (<i>Metete fierro hasta el fondo</i>)	Guapo tradition	<i>Fierro</i> (iron/metal) was a common phallic metaphor in the lunfardo of the period. Guapo refers to the figure of the tough man of the arrabal — the working-class outskirts. The title describes deep penetration in direct terms. No lyrics preserved.
Hard / Erect! (<i>¡Al palo!</i>)	Eduardo Arolas	<i>Al palo</i> designated an erection in the lunfardo of the period — literally 'to the pole', meaning fully erect. Eduardo Arolas (1892–1924) was one of the most celebrated bandoneon players and composers of the Guardia Vieja. ⁷ His presence in this corpus is not incidental: the brothel and the professional music world were, in this period, the same social environment. Musicians played in brothels; brothel culture produced musicians.
Come Here and Blow My Candle (<i>Vení, soplame la vela</i>)	Cafishio tradition	<i>Cafishio</i> is lunfardo for pimp. The candle (<i>vela</i>) is a phallic metaphor; 'blow' (<i>soplar</i>) refers to oral sex. The title is an instruction from a pimp to a woman in the brothel. No lyrics preserved.
Shave My Beard (<i>Afeitame la barba</i>)	Piringundín tradition	<i>Piringundín</i> : a low-end dance venue, typically a café by day and a brothel annex by night, of probable Genoese origin, common in the La Boca neighborhood. 'Shave my beard' operates as a sexual double entendre, with the beard standing in for pubic hair. Instrumental survival.
The Iron Blow (<i>El fierrazo</i>)	Riverside tradition	Same semantic field as 'Push the Iron All the Way In': the iron/metal as a phallic metaphor was standard in the brothel lunfardo. The suffix <i>-azo</i> in Spanish indicates a forceful blow or strike, intensifying the already explicit meaning.

Category D — Exclusively Oral Survival

No score, no publisher's record, no printed documentation of any kind. These cases reached us solely through the memory of musicians who worked in the brothel world and were

⁷Arolas, Eduardo (1892–1924). Bandoneon player and composer, one of the central figures of the Guardia Vieja. The bandoneon, a type of concertina brought to Argentina by German immigrants, became the defining instrument of tango. Arolas's presence in this corpus is not incidental: the brothel and the professional music scene were, in this period, the same social world.

interviewed decades later. They are the most fragile evidence in the corpus — and the most direct.

Title (EN / ES)	Author / Reference	Analysis
How the Little Girl Loves the Gut! (<i>¿Cómo le gusta la tripa a la nena!</i>)	Brothel tradition	<i>Tripa</i> (gut/intestine) was used as a phallic metaphor. The phrase 'the little girl' (<i>la nena</i>) places the scene in the brothel, where young women were a common subject of obscene song. Documented by oral tradition only.
Bartolo Plays the Flute / Bartolo's Flute (<i>Bartolo toca la flauta / La flauta de Bartolo</i>)	Oral tradition	The original lyrics ran: 'Bartolo plays the flute with a single hole.' The flute with one hole is a transparent phallic image. This song later became a children's nursery rhyme — the same text, the same melody, an entirely different context of reception. No modification of the words was necessary: changing the audience changed the meaning completely. It is one of the most striking examples in this corpus of how semantic neutralization can operate without any alteration to the original material.
The Corn Cob with Hair (<i>El choclo con pelos</i>)	Brothel tradition	A brothel variant of <i>El Choclo</i> . The original version ran: 'a corn cob with hair and a red tip.' This is anatomical description without any metaphorical mediation — the phallic image is spelled out in physical detail. The contrast with Villoldo's carefully camouflaged version illustrates the distance between what circulated inside the brothel and what could be published outside it. Documented by oral tradition only.
The Whip Stroke (<i>El fustazo</i>)	Oral tradition	<i>Fustazo</i> : a whip stroke, used here as a phallic metaphor. The suffix <i>-azo</i> denotes a forceful strike. No score or editorial record known.

Cross-Analysis: Semantic Fields of the Corpus

Beyond the mechanism of survival or censorship, the corpus can be read by semantic field. What appears is not merely a collection of obscenities: it is a vocabulary that maps the body, the sexual act and the brothel space with a precision that no official document of the period permitted itself. Reading it this way reveals which aspects of that reality popular language chose to name — and with what resources.

The most densely populated field is that of phallic metaphor. The repertoire is both systematic and wide-ranging: musical instruments (the flute, the candle), tools and metals (the iron, the whip stroke), foods (the corn cob), measurements (seven inches), physical states (erect). The variety reflects a practical necessity: it was essential to name what could not be named directly in any public register, and lunfardo developed for that purpose a remarkable lexical arsenal. The cases in this field include *El Choclo*, *Sacudime la poronga*, *Siete pulgadas*, *El fierrazo*, *Metete fierro hasta el fondo*, *La flauta de Bartolo*, *¡Al palo!* and *El fustazo*.

Female genital vocabulary is notably underrepresented in the preserved titles. This does not reflect an absence in the original corpus but rather greater effectiveness of censorship in that

register: references to the female body were apparently considered more threatening and were more systematically suppressed. The documented cases — *Concha sucia*, *La concha de la Lora*, *La budinera* — all show highly visible substitution operations. The asymmetry between the abundance of phallic metaphors and the scarcity of female genital references is in itself a historical datum: it reflects the point of view from which this repertoire was produced and consumed.

Titles describing the sexual act range from the oblique ('shake my venetian blind') to the completely explicit ('let it die inside'). This variation does not reflect differences of taste but differences in venue: the most explicit material circulated in the most closed spaces, where there was no risk of a bourgeois ear overhearing; the more euphemistic titles could risk a semi-public venue without causing a direct scandal.

A specific and particularly valuable subset names the brothel space or its internal economy directly. *El Queco* names the brothel without mediation. *Dame la lata* ('give me the token') is the only case in the entire corpus that documents the internal economic organization of the *lupanar*: the token was the instrument through which the establishment controlled the transaction between client and woman, separating the payment from the act itself.⁸ That this payment system left a trace in a tango title is an archival datum that no official document of the period captures with comparable clarity.

Finally, the ethnic and trafficking reference appears concentrated in a single documented case: *La concha de la Lora*. Censorship operated on this title at three simultaneous levels — the genital, the ethnic and the trafficking — making it the case of greatest historical and semantic density in the corpus. The replacement with 'the face of the moon' was not a moral cleansing: it was an erasure of evidence.

Case Study: El Choclo (Villoldo, 1905)

El Choclo is the most instructive case in the corpus because it makes the mechanism of cultural domestication visible in its most elaborate form. Unlike the Category A cases, where an external agent intervened to modify the title or lyrics, here Villoldo himself constructed

⁸The municipal regulation of 1875 established the system of licensed brothels in Buenos Aires. Its primary purpose was not the protection of the women who worked in them but the control of venereal disease among male clients. Women were required to register, pay licensing fees and submit to medical examinations at a dedicated syphilis clinic that opened in 1888. The predictable result was that the majority operated clandestinely. See Guy, Donna J. *Sex and Danger in Buenos Aires: Prostitution, Family, and Nation in Argentina*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1991.

the cover. There was no victim and no external perpetrator: there was a musician who understood the rules of the market and used them deliberately.⁹

The original lyrics (1905) — original Spanish preserved

Note: The lyrics are kept in Spanish because the rural camouflage mechanism — which is the analytical object of this case study — only functions in the original language. A translation would destroy the very thing being analyzed.

*De un grano nace la planta que más tarde nos da el choclo
por eso de la garganta dijo que estaba humilloso.*

*Y yo como no soy otro más que un tanguero de fama
murmuro con alborozo está muy de la banana.*

*Hay choclos que tienen las espigas de oro
que son las que adoro con tierna pasión,
cuando trabajando llenito de abrojos
estoy con rastros como humilde peón.*

*A veces el choclo asa en los fogones
calma las pasiones y dichas de amor,
cuando algún paisano lo está cocinando
y otro está cebando un buen cimarrón.*

*Luego que la humita está preparada,
bajo la enramada se oye un pericón,
y junto al alero, de un rancho deshecho
surge de algún pecho la alegre canción.*

Source: 1905 version, Ángel Villoldo.

Rough prose translation of the lyric content (for orientation only): 'From a grain grows the plant that later gives us the corn cob... There are corn cobs with golden tassels that I adore... Sometimes the corn cob roasting on the fire calms the passions and joys of love... Once the humita [a corn-based dish] is ready, under the arbor you hear a pericón [a folk dance], and from the chest of a broken-down ranch house rises a cheerful song.'

The mechanism: deliberate camouflage, not external censorship

The obvious question when reading this lyric is: where is the obscenity? It is not there. And that is precisely the correct answer, because the mechanism at work here is not censorship from outside but deliberate camouflage from within. The music of *El Choclo* already

⁹The complete lyrics of 'El Choclo' in their 1905 version are reproduced and analyzed in Ferrer, Horacio. *El libro del tango*. Buenos Aires: Galerna, 1980, vol. II. The interpretation of the rural camouflage as a deliberate authorial strategy — rather than a coincidence or an external imposition — is a hypothesis of the author of this catalogue.

circulated in the brothel world with its double meaning embedded in the collective imagination. The title — 'the corn cob', understood as the penis — was the joke. To publish the score legally, to have it circulate in theatres and salons, Villoldo needed a lyric that would pass the filter of publishers and the League of Decency. He therefore wrote a deliberately innocuous text.

Every word in the lyric belongs to a rural vocabulary: corn tassels, stubble fields, farm laborers, peasants, cooking fires, *humita* (a traditional corn-based dish wrapped in corn husks), *pericón* (a traditional folk dance), ranch houses, *cimarrón* (unsweetened mate, the traditional South American herbal drink). It is a postcard of the Argentine countryside without a single word that refers to the urban, brothel or immigrant world where the music actually circulated. The choice is not accidental: the rural was the semantic field most remote from the brothel in the imagination of the period. This is the mechanism this catalogue calls the 'rural shield'.

There are, however, two fractures in that innocent surface. The first: 'Y yo como no soy otro más que un tanguero de fama / murmuro con alborozo está muy de la banana' — roughly, 'And I, being nothing but a celebrated tango man, murmur with delight that it's very much like the banana.' Villoldo names himself in the lyric as a *tanguero de fama* — a renowned tango man — and uses the expression *muy de la banana*, which in the lunfardo of the period carried sexual connotations.¹⁰ This verse is an internal signature: Villoldo is winking at the audience that already knows what *choclo* means, while appearing to write bucolic verse about crop yields. The rest of the lyric is camouflage; this verse is the author's true mark.

The second fracture: 'calma las pasiones y dichas de amor' — 'it calms the passions and joys of love.' In the rural context this reads as a metaphor for the nourishment provided by a simple peasant meal. In the context of someone who knows the title, it describes the brothel as the place where passions are calmed. The lyric says and does not say the same thing simultaneously.

What this case demonstrates with precision is how cultural domestication functions when performed by the artist himself. No external force intervened. Villoldo simultaneously produced two versions of the same object: one for the brothel and one for the legal market, with a signature in the lyric legible only to those already on the inside. The camouflage was so successful that it erased the original. Today *El Choclo* is the quintessential tango for state occasions, embassy receptions and tourist shows — and the corn cob is just a corn cob.

¹⁰The expression *muy de la banana* carried clear sexual connotations in the Buenos Aires lunfardo of the period. The verse works as an internal signature: Villoldo names himself as a *tanguero de fama* (a celebrated tango man) and embeds a signal that is legible only to those who already know what the title means. It is the author winking at his own audience while appearing to write bucolic verse.

Notes on Sources and Transmission

The survival of this corpus is in itself a historiographical fact. There is no centralized archive of obscene tangos. What exists are scattered references in secondary sources, accounts from musicians interviewed in the second half of the twentieth century, and comparisons between sanitized versions and inferences about the originals. That this catalogue can exist at all is the result of a chain of transmission that is fragile and, at several points, accidental.

José Gobello, founder of the Academia Porteña del Lunfardo (the Porteño Academy of Lunfardo), conducted systematic interviews with Guardia Vieja musicians who still remembered original titles and lyrics. His oral compilation is the primary source for several Category D cases — the most direct evidence available.¹¹ Without those interviews, conducted while firsthand testimony was still possible, a significant portion of the corpus would have vanished entirely.

Early scores, when they existed, circulated in very small print runs, often without a publisher's name or imprint. The mainstream music publishing industry in Buenos Aires did not print this material; what reached libraries and collections was the sanitized version. The League of Decency held no direct policing power, but its sustained pressure on publishers was sufficient to make self-censorship operate as a preventive mechanism.¹² What this catalogue recovers is what that mechanism did not manage to suppress entirely.

*Mariano A. Niemand is a historian and educator. This catalogue was prepared as a working document for the **Contango** lecture series, of which he is the author, dedicated to the social and cultural history of tango.*

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¹¹Gobello, José, op. cit. Without the interviews Gobello conducted when firsthand testimony was still possible, a significant portion of the Category D corpus would have vanished entirely.

¹²The self-censorship mechanism generated by the League of Decency among Buenos Aires publishers was arguably more effective than any direct enforcement could have been. Publishers did not need to be threatened: they understood what was and was not printable, and they acted accordingly.